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English Language Proficiency and Individual Economic Enhancement

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Abstract

English as one of the international languages has many benefits that can be felt by its users both from a social and economic perspective. This study aims to dig up information about the effect of English language skills on the economic level of the family using the literature review or literature review method. The results of this study explain that being able to work in a multinational/international company and several elite agencies can have an impact on improving a person's economy and society. It's just that one of the requirements that someone must have to get in these companies is to have the ability to speak English both orally and in writing.

Keywords: *English language, proficiency, Economic Enhancement*

INTRODUCTION

Language plays a very important role for every individual. Everyday human activities are inseparable from language because humans have one need, namely to communicate with one another. In daily communication, language becomes an inevitable necessity to facilitate the activities of one human being with another human being. In a state, language becomes a symbol of the freedom of a nation. Upholding one language, Indonesian is one of the sounds of the youth plede declared several decades ago by our founding fathers.

Language becomes very important because as social beings who always interact with one another within the household, community and even across islands as well countries. We do it so that our interlocutors can fully understand what our goals or intentions are to avoid misunderstandings in interacting.

Alat komunikasi yang paling handal ampuh dalam kehidupan bersama dalam suatu masyarakat adalah bahasa. Manusia memakai bahasa dalam seluruh kesehariannya. Bahasa menjadi begitu penting dalam keseluruhan hidup manusia. Jika penggunaan bahasa secara minimal dapat dipahami sesuai maksud dan tujuan dari si pembicara maka bahasa sudah mencapai tujuan dalam menyampaikan sebuah pesan dalam komunikasi. Dalam kondisi resmi, seluruh pembicaraan harus mengikuti pola-pola tertentu. Dalam mempelajari maksud dan tujuan tertentu di dalam berkomunikasi baik secara lisan atau pun tulisan, konteks utama yang perlu diperhatikan oleh penutur adalah tujuan berbahasa dapat tercapai atau mencapai tujuan (Mariani: 2022)

The most reliable and powerful communication tool in living together in a society is language. Humans use language in their entire daily lives. Language becomes so important in the whole of human life. If the minimum use of language can be understood according to the intent and purpose of the speaker, then the language has achieved its goal in conveying a message in communication. Under official conditions, all conversations must follow a certain pattern. In studying certain aims and objectives in communicating both verbally and in writing, the main context that needs to be considered by speakers is that the language goals can be achieved or achieve goals (Mariani: 2022)

Vanya (2022) says that humans use language in various situations and conditions. Through language, humans can talk and establish relationships. The role of language in human life is very large. Without language, humans will not be able to understand messages or information, know and call names of people or objects, to tell their experiences. Therefore, language is an important communication tool and it cannot be separated from human life.

Not limited to that, one's language skills can actually have an impact on improving one's economy or even a nation itself. As stated by Harunasari (2021) that the growth of foreign language-based content creators which are currently popular among young people is proof of the close relationship between foreign language skills and opportunities for work and creative opportunities. Look at several YouTubers who succeed in catching subscribers and viewers attention such as Naila Farhana, Londo Kampung, Sarah Johnson, Fiki Naki and others.

They are all just a few of the many young successful people who have inspired many people to become a place and source of learning foreign languages that are not limited in time, place and cost, but instead give a bonus of joy. Delivered in their own distinctive style, they often even invite the audience to laugh together at deliberation of their silliness in learning foreign languages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Language

Fachrurrozi and Erta Mahyuddin (2011:6) put forward several definitions of language, namely: (a) language is a collection of sounds that have a specific purpose and are organized by grammatical rules (b) language is an everyday conversational expression of most people spoken at normal speed (c) language is a system for expressing meaning (d) language is a set of grammatical rules and language consists of parts.

Siahaan (2008:7) explained Language is a unique human inheritance that plays the very important role in human's life, such as in thinking, communicating ideas, and negotiating with the others. In general, language use is as a tool to communicate. The communication process will run well when the two communicating parties are equipped with knowledge of language and language skills. Mastery of vocabulary and grammar are two aspects that have to be possessed by someone who wants to learn a language, especially a foreign language. Meanwhile, to be active communicators, the skills that need to be master are including speaking skills, listening skills, writing skills, and reading skills.

Raharjo (2015) added that there are many definitions made by experts about language, depending on the emphasis but it can be concluded that language is an arbitrary speech-sound symbol system that is used to communicate by the people who use it.

Ronald Wardhaugh in Raharjo (2015) defines language as "a system of arbitrary vocal symbols used for human communication". This definition emphasizes that in essence language is speech, not writing, which combines sound and meaning. There is no relation between symbol, sound and meaning. That what is meant by arbitrary, as one of the characteristic of language.

Raharjo continued that the language we use is actually the same as the sound that animals make. For example, when a cat meows, it is communicating with its friends or environment. Likewise, when a student screams in front of the class, he is conveying something to his friends or the people around him. Therefore, cat sounds and students' screams are actually a form of communication, because both contain the message to be conveyed. But cat sounds cannot be called language. While the screams of students are called language. Therefore, it can be said that a cat makes a sound, while a student speaks.

Mastery of English Language

According to Chaer (2013) English is the main international language which is the lingua franca of all nations in the world, so if we want to enter the international arena, we must master English well. So, by being able to speak English we can easily communicate with other people around the world. It would be better if Indonesian sons and daughters mastered foreign languages, but they also had to master good Indonesian too.

Murais (2003) added that English is not only an academic requirement for limited mastery in aspects of language knowledge, but also as the language of science and technology. This means that English is used to communicate and is extracted in science and technology. It seems that most are in English, and even various technical documents and guidelines for the use and improvement of English-speaking devices. (Maurais, 2003 in Seong, Language Appreciation and Development of National Identity)

Reporting from Cambridge Assessment English, they have conducted a survey of 5,300 workers in 38 countries. It was found that the ability to speak English is one of the most important abilities worldwide.

Still, quoted from cambridgeenglish.org, it states that in countries where English is not the official language, half of employers say that there are career benefits for people with good English skills. These benefits cover

- 1) Better starting salary (50% employer)
- 2) Faster progress through employment levels (50% of employers)
- 3) Higher salary increases (49% of employers)

Even in countries where English is not an official language, around two in three workers say English is important for running a business.

Facts:

- a) About 85% of international organizations use English for their daily work
- b) More than 80% of academic journals are written in English

The ability to speak good and correct English is very important in the digitalization era like today. English as a global lingua franca will also provide broad insights and make it easier to do activities with the international community.

Zubaidah (2021) writing on sindonews.com, Director of MNC Kapital Jessica Tanoesoedibjo said, mastering English is important because in the digital era like today it makes the world narrower. This happens because now interconnection from all over the world is easier to do. "Especially now that there is a pandemic, it is increasingly visible that communication can be done online. Each home can be connected globally.

According to English First (2021) to measure a person's proficiency or mastery of the English language internationally can be done with the CEFR system. CEFR stands for Common European Framework of Reference for Languages. Still quoted from EF, there are six levels in CEFR, namely: A1 Beginner, A2 Elementary, B1 Intermediate, B2 Upper Intermediate, C1 Advanced, and C2 Proficient.

C2 or professional/expert is the sixth and final level of the CEFR. Someone who is at this level has a position equivalent to a native speaker. That means the person concerned can use English in any situation and condition.

Ekonomi

Sukirno (1999) argues that economic growth means the development of activities in the economy which causes the goods and services produced in society to increase and the prosperity of society to increase. The problem of economic growth can be seen as a long-term macroeconomic problem from one period to another. 1 Meanwhile, according to Lincoln Arsyad, economic growth is defined as an increase in gross domestic product (GDP)/gross national product (GNP) regardless of whether the increase is greater or less than the rate of population growth, or whether changes in economic structure occur or not.

Meanwhile, according to Ali Ibrahim Hasyim in his book *Makro Enomoni* (2016), economic growth can be interpreted as a process of changing a country's economic conditions on an ongoing basis towards a better state during a certain period. There are three basic components needed for a nation's economic growth; (1) The continuous increase in the supply of goods; (2) advanced technology as the main factor that determines the degree of growth in providing a variety of goods to the population; (3) the widespread and efficient use of technology requires adjustments in the institutional and ideological fields, so that the innovations produced by human science and technology can be utilized appropriately.

According to Nawawi (2009), Improvement means progress, change, improvement. While the economy has the basic word "Oikos" which means household and "Nomos" which means rules so the economy implies rules that apply to meet the necessities of life in one household. From the above understanding it can be concluded that an increase in pre-community is indicated by an increase in community welfare to meet the necessities of life.

The community's economy is a group of human groups who already have a life order, norms, customs applied in their environment. This is according to Noor (1997).

According to Zulkarnain (2003), populist economy is an economic system that must be adhered to in accordance with the philosophy of our country which concerns two aspects, namely justice and economic democracy, and side with the people.

RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is to use the method of literature review or literature review. Literature Review is a reference list of all types of references such as books, journal papers, articles, dissertations, theses, theses, hand outs, laboratory manuals, and other scientific works. According to Pohan (2007), the purpose of this activity (the preparation of a literature review) is to collect scientific data and information, in the form of theories, methods or approaches that have developed and have been documented in the form of books, journals, manuscripts, records, historical records, documents, and others contained in the library. According to Sugiyono (2017), literature study is an important step where after a researcher determines a research topic, the next step is to conduct theoretical studies and references related to the research being conducted. In research on language as a communication tool, it seeks to describe matters relating to language as a communication tool in which it explains the function of language as a communication tool, and communication in daily life explains why we communicate, and the language used when communicating in daily activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English Language and Improving of the Economy

English as an international language is still a language that is a requirement for someone who wants to study or work abroad, especially in England and America and in general on the European continent.

TOEFL and IELTS are international standard language proficiency tests still used to measure a person's language skills. Quoted from *wallstreetenglish*, stated that TOEFL and IELTS are the two most popular of the many English Language Proficiency Tests for Non-Native Speakers. Both tests will test your basic abilities such as reading, writing, speaking and listening. However, there are distinct differences between the two tests in terms of structure, scores and approach.

Work is one way to improve the economy of the family and society. In terms of work, of course it will be very different for someone who has English skills and does not have English skills. For example, if you want to work at an embassy, one of the special requirements required for prospective applicants is being able to speak English well both orally and in writing.

- II. **PERSYARATAN KHUSUS:**
- A. **Pegawai setempat Penerangan dan Sosial-Budaya**
1. WN Indonesia yang memiliki status penduduk tetap/*permanent resident* di Kroasia yang masih berlaku, atau WN Kroasia.
 2. Memiliki ijazah minimal Diploma 3 atau S-1/ sederajat.
 3. Bagi calon pegawai setempat WN Kroasia mampu berbahasa Inggris dan Kroasia dengan baik, lisan maupun tulisan dan lebih diutamakan bagi yang memiliki kemampuan berbahasa Indonesia.
 4. Bagi calon pegawai setempat WN Indonesia mampu berbahasa Indonesia dan Inggris dengan baik, lisan maupun tulisan dan lebih diutamakan bagi yang memiliki kemampuan berbahasa Kroasia.
 5. Mengerti Teknologi Informasi dan dapat mengoperasikan komputer (menguasai *Microsoft Office*).
 6. Diutamakan yang memiliki kompetensi sebagai berikut:
 - a. Memiliki pengetahuan umum mengenai Indonesia.
 - b. Memiliki ketertarikan seni dan budaya Indonesia.

Source: *Kemlu.go.id* 2019

It quotes from the disnakertrans.ntbprov.go.id page (2020) it is said that there are several important reasons why employees must have English skills:

- 1) Build connections
- 2) International business expansion
- 3) Ease of negotiation with foreign parties
- 4) Improving agency standards

From this explanation, we can conclude that the Province of NTB also supports and prioritizes prospective employees who have English skills in both government agencies and private institutions.

The same thing was conveyed by Reisha (2019) quoted from detik.com, stating that the results of the survey 'English Proficiency and Indonesia's Position in the Global Workforce' show that English communication skills are considered important by HR professionals in 96% of Indonesian companies.

This means that 96% of employers see that every HR professional in Indonesia must have English communication skills to support performance in every position where they are placed.

Reisha continued that the demand for English skills is quite high in Indonesia compared to other countries surveyed and most HR leaders said that proficiency in English is required, both for senior and entry-level positions.

Other information provided by Reisha said that 86% of multinational companies provide training for their employees to improve proficiency in using English. In other words, it can be concluded that if you want to be able to work in a multinational company, you must already have the ability to speak English.

Sumber: Detik.com

Tanamal (2021) adds that there are several benefits of working in a multinational company, one of which is Salary and Benefits, meaning that if someone works in a multinational company, the salary offered tends to be higher than that of local companies. Multinational companies also provide personal death insurance benefits to their employees.

From the explanation above, we can conclude that if someone works in a multinational company, they will get a salary that tends to be high, which allows each employee to be able to get a better life and family economy.

The practical and effective methods to master English

Chamot (1987) provides an overview that learning strategies of a language are conscious behaviors or actions. Language learning strategies are techniques, approaches or activities used by students to facilitate learning, by considering linguistics and information content to achieve learning goals.

Meanwhile, Hismanoglu (2000: 21) states his opinion that the definition of language learning strategies includes behaviors and thoughts that deliberately used by learners during learning to help them understand, learn, or remember new information.

According to Oxford (1990:14), there are two ways to use second language learning strategies. The first is a direct learning strategy (direct strategy) and the second is an indirect learning strategy (indirect strategy).

Direct language learning strategies include memory strategies where the strategies used are to remember and receive new information. The second indirect learning strategy is a cognitive strategy where strategies used to understand language and produce or produce language.

Next is the direct learning strategy includes metacognitive strategies, affective strategies and social strategies.

First, metacognitive strategies are indirect strategies for learning a second language. This strategy emphasizes the importance of the learner to concentrate on learning language, organize and plan language learning, and evaluate how to learn the language.

Second, this learning strategy includes emotions, attitudes, motivations, and values in the process of learning a second language. There are several ways that learners can achieve satisfactory results in learning a second language.

Finally, social strategy is a language learning strategy that indirectly means that students have entered the social world.

Rost (2002) added other strategies to improve English speaking skills such as activities: 1. Demonstration 2. Personal stories 3. Interview 4. Telephone 5. Story map 6. Group survey 7. Short speech.

From the several theories mentioned above, we can conclude that improving one's English communication skills can be done directly or indirectly and based on the experience of the author, what needs to be done in Indonesia to improve everyone's language skills, especially employees, is to provide space to apply the use of English directly.

CONCLUSION

English as an international language is not only a means of communication. If someone has the ability to speak English then that person has added value as a professional. In the world of work, someone with English language skills has a much wider opportunity to be able to work in a company or agency that offers a far greater salary and benefits compared to local companies. If someone works in a multinational or even international level, it is highly likely that they can also improve their family's economic level.

SUGGESTION

In Indonesia, starting from the kindergarten level, children have been introduced to English. They continue to study English at Elementary School (*SD*) then Junior High School (*SMP*) to High School (*SMA*). We can see the facts on the ground there are still many high school graduates do not have the ability to communicate in English properly and correctly, even though they have studied for years. Reflecting from the author experiences of as an English teacher with more than ten years experience this is because while at school students are taught to use strategies indirectly so, in the end they lack of space and exposure to apply English in daily life.

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